

The interplay between working memory and speech recognition declines over time

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In summary, the preliminary findings suggests that individuals with higher WMC at T1 experienced less decline in SPIN at T2.

However, SPIN performance over time seems not to be related decline in WMC, suggesting a potential protective role of WMC against cognitive decline in the auditory domain.

Figure 1
Individual performance in the HINT (left panel) RSpan (right panel) for the two test occasions.

Background

Age-related changes in auditory and cognitive functions are well-documented, with increased hearing thresholds (e.g., Wiley et al., 2008) and reduced working memory capacity (WMC; e.g., Wingfield et al., 1988) among older adults. Moreover, aging has been linked to poorer speech recognition in noise (e.g., Marsja et al., 2022), highlighting the multifaceted impact of age on auditory and cognitive domains. Our study examined the dynamic relationship between auditory and cognitive changes over time to shed light on the direction of influence between the two. To this aim, we employed change score modeling.

Methods

We used preliminary data from two test occasions (T1 and T2) in the n200 study (Rönnerberg et al., 2016).

Participants

One-hundred and eleven participants that participated in both T1 and T2. See Table 1 for sample characteristics.

Table 1

Descriptive statistics for age, reading span score, HINT snr, gender and pure-tone average (worse ear).

	T1	T2
Characteristic	N = 111 ¹	N = 111 ¹
Age	61 (8)	67 (8)
RSpan	16.9 (3.7)	15.0 (4.5)
HINT	-3.12 (0.79)	-1.68 (1.95)
Gender		
female	53 (48%)	50 (46%)
male	58 (52%)	58 (54%)
PTA4	14 (7)	18 (10)

¹Mean (SD); n (%)

Measurements

We used the **Reading Span (RSpan)** test to measure WMC. In the RSpan test, participants are presented with sentences and are required to remember the final word of each sentence while making judgments about the sentences (e.g., whether they make sense). See Figure 1,

right panel, for performance in T1 and T2.

Figure 2
Path diagram for the latent change score model with standardized estimates.

We used the Swedish **Hearing in Noise Test (HINT)** sentences as a Speech in Noise (SPIN), comprising 250 sentences divided into 25 lists. Each list contains 20 phonemically balanced sentences ranging from 3 to 7 words. The target speech was presented at 65 dB SPL, with noise levels adjusted adaptively in 2 dB steps. Our study followed an adaptive procedure targeting Speech Reception Threshold (SRT) for 50% correct whole sentences. After a practice trial, participants encountered 20 sentences in steady-state noise (SSN). Mean SRTs were calculated based on signal-to-noise ratios (SNRs) from the last 15 sentences.

Latent Change Score Modeling

We used latent change score modeling to investigate dynamic changes over two time points in WMC and SPIN. This enabled us to explore the reciprocal relationship between WMC and SPIN.

Results

- ✓ WMC at T1 predicted changes in WMC, negatively.
- ✓ SPIN at T1 predicted changes in SPIN, negatively.
- ✓ Interestingly, WMC at T1 predicted changes in SPIN, negatively, whereas HINT at T1 did not significantly predict changes in WMC.

The results are depicted in Figure 2.

References

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